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Master in Data Management
and Curation

Implementation of FAIR by design principles for data acquisition and storage at CNR-IFN Milano

Candidate:

Giovanni Gallerani

Trieste, 2025-05-28

Supervisors:

Michele Devetta

Tommaso Rodani

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About me

Master's degree in Artificial Intelligence, Data Science and Big Data

Università degli Studi di Ferrara

September 2023 – Now

Junior Software Developer Intern

Datalogic - Lippo di Calderara di Reno (BO)

May 2023 – September 2023

Bachelor's degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering

Università degli Studi di Ferrara

Thesis on NoSQL databases and performance comparison between MongoDB and MySQL.

September 2019 – March 2023

Hobbies: videogames, comics, tabletop RPGs, drawing, listening to music, cinema.

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FAIR by design progress so far

Each experimental station is custom-built in-house and has its own acquisition software that save experimental data in HDF5 files.

Distributed control infrastructure based on the TANGO system

- All the experimental parameters of the devices integrated into the system are easily accessible via Python.
- All the metadata are available automatically.

TANGO logo from tango-controls.org

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Limitations

- 1) The structure of HDF5 files varies between experimental stations.
- 2) No automated data saving mechanism.
- 3) Traditional paper logbooks are still in use.

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Proposed data flow (to address 1 and 2)

User initiate an experiment within a lab specifying a Laboratory ID and receiving an Experiment ID

The experimental station insert data and metadata in NeXus files according to the selected application definition

The NeXus files are sent to a supervisor program running on the local server, specifying Laboratory ID and Experiment ID

The supervisor validates the NeXus file, stores it in the appropriate directory and makes it read-only

Files stored on the local server are periodically synchronized with OFED

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Initial TODO list

- Select a NeXus application definition for use across laboratories' beamlines.
- Implement a relational database with Laboratory ID and Experiment ID as keys and a web interface to request and manage them using Django.
- Develop a supervisor that runs on the local server and interact with the database in order to save the NeXus files in the correct directories.
- Develop a Python interface for interacting with the supervisor.

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NeXus application definition for UDynI

- The chosen application definition is an implementation of **NXoptical_spectroscopy**, an application definition originally proposed by the NeXus-FAIRmat project.
- Only the fields related to ultrafast spectroscopy have been retained.
- The development of the application definition was carried out in collaboration with Laura Costantini, a fellow master's student that was working on a NeXus application definition for ultrafast spectroscopy in CNR-ISM Roma.

FAIRmat logo from <https://www.fairmat-nfdi.eu/fairmat/>

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Problems with writing NeXus files manually

- Specifying verbose internal paths.
- Selecting the appropriate data types for each Nxfield by looking at the not so friendly documentation.
- Carefully following the conventions, non of which are forced by the file structure itself.

These problems create a **barrier to adoption** and lead to **fragile and hard to maintain code**.

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Updated TODO list

- ~~Select a NeXus application definition for use across laboratories' beamlines.~~
- Create a tool for easy NeXus files creation.

- Implement a relational database with Laboratory ID and Experiment ID as keys and a web interface to request and manage them using Django.

- Develop a supervisor that runs on the local server and interact with the database in order to save the NeXus files in the correct directories.
- Develop a Python interface for interacting with the supervisor.

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udyninexus

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udyninexus

A Python package for facilitating the creation of NeXus-compliant data files creation made for UDynI research group.

- Enable users to generate NeXus files, following the UDynI implementation of the NXOptical_Spectroscopy, by using a high-level class-based API.
- Implements type validation for each field and warn the user if the NeXus file has missing fields with actionable error messages.
- Can be used without knowing how a NeXus file is made, only interacting with few simple classes is needed.

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udyninexus DEMO

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A digital laboratory logbook for UDynI

- As the udyninexus package matured it became evident that a database for storing information about the laboratories and experiment would still be needed for future supervisor integration.
- This realization prompted a re-evaluation of priorities: rather than implementing the supervisor immediately, the focus shifted to building a web application allowing users to manage experiments, sample and maintain a digital logbook.

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Updated TODO list

- ~~Select a NeXus application definition for use across laboratories' beamlines.~~
- ~~Create a tool for easy NeXus files creation.~~

- Implement a relational database with Laboratory ID and Experiment ID as keys and a web interface to request and manage them using Django.

- Develop a digital laboratory logbook web app.
- Implement REST APIs for making the interaction between the web app and the supervisor possible.

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LabLogbook

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LabLogbook

A web application that allow users to manage experiments, track measurements, and document laboratory activity in a structured and centralized way through a digital logbook.

Offers both interactive web interface and RESTful APIs.

- Implemented using the Django framework.
- Rather than building a standalone system, the new application was integrated into an existing Django project already in use within the laboratories for user management, project tracking and time monitoring.

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LabLogbook DEMO

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Overview of the work done

- Implementation of **NXoptical_spectroscopy** application definition for the laboratories.
- **udyninexus**: a Python package developed for simplify the generation of NeXus files. Reduces the risk of errors in the writing of acquisition software for the beamlines.
- **LabLogbook**: Django-based web application for managing samples, experiments and implement a digital logbook all with a user-friendly interface. The application functionalities are completed by a set of RESTful API for seamless interaction with automated systems.

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Advantages brought to the lab by the work

- Standardized file generation.
- Centralized documentation.
- Collaborative commenting system.
- Automation via REST APIs.
- Improved research quality.

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Future developments

The application definition used in the laboratories could be extended, and with it udyninexus.

More types of instrument could be supported, starting from stages, instruments that move the laser sources in time.

Implementation of the supervisor

The supervisor should check if the Nexus files received from the experimental station are well formed in comparison with the correct application definition for that experiment, and then automatically store them.

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Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

Nano Foundries Fine Analysis
Digital Infrastructure

Pathogen Readiness Platform
for CERIC-ERIC Upgrade

Thanks to the SISSA school and AREA staff.

Thanks to my supervisors and laboratory staff.

Thanks to all my colleagues, friends, and family.

Thanks to all the kind strangers on Stack Overflow.

Thanks for your attention!

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